

EPR Spectra of Copper(II) Complexes with Biguanide Derivatives[†]

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Copper(II) complexes of quadridentate ligands, *viz.*, ethylenedibiguanide, trimethylenedibiguanide, *m*-phenylenedibiguanide, piperazinedibiguanide, and bidentate ligand phenylbiguanide have been studied by epr spectroscopy in polycrystalline form and in the corresponding Ni^{II} complex matrix. Epr spectra of the complexes in the corresponding Ni^{II} complex matrix exhibit nine nitrogen superhyperfine lines on the high field 3/2 $\leftrightarrow$ 3/2 copper hyperfine splitting components indicating the presence of four equivalent nitrogen atoms around the Cu^{II} ion. The evaluation of the covalency parameters from the epr data indicates that the unpaired electron of Cu^{II} spends about 31–36% of its time in the nitrogen donor sites of the ligands. The epr spectra of the complexes suggest the presence of CuN₄ coordination sphere in the complexes. A comparison of the bonding parameters of the Cu^{II} dibiguanide complexes with those of the Cu^{II} complexes of biguanide and phenylbiguanide indicates that the bridging group in quadridentate dibiguanides has negligible effect on the epr spectra and bonding parameters. A comparison of the bonding parameters of the present complexes with those of the Cu^{II} complexes of tetrapenylporphine and phthalocyanine indicates that biguanides and dibiguanides rank among strong field ligands.

BIGUANIDES (1) and their metal complexes exhibit medicinal properties¹ and are used as hypoglycaemic and antimalarial agents. Biguanides and dibiguanides (2–5) are considered to be strong field ligands. Biguanides have stabilised a large number of unusual oxidation states of transition metal ions (Co^I, Ni^{III}, Ni^{IV}, Mn^{IV}, Ag^{III}, Au^{III}, Mo^{III} *etc.*) and have produced metal complexes of very high formation constant values². Metal complexes of biguanides exhibit aromatic character³. The

introduction of a bridging group connecting two biguanide molecules, *e.g.* in ethylenedibiguanide (2) is expected to influence the stability and bonding parameters in dibiguanide complexes. We report here the epr spectra of Cu^{II} doped in diamagnetic Ni^{II} complexes of ethylenedibiguanide (2), trimethylenedibiguanide (3), *m*-phenylenedibiguanide (4), piperazinedibiguanide (5) and phenylbiguanide (6) in order to see the effect of bridging groups in the epr spectra and bonding parameters of the Cu^{II} complexes of biguanide and dibiguanides. Epr spectra of Cu^{II} complex of biguanide have been reported earlier⁴.

Experimental

Ethylenedibiguanide sulphate, trimethylenedibiguanide sulphate, *m*-phenylenedibiguanide sulphate and piperazinedibiguanide sulphate and their Cu^{II} complexes were prepared according to the published procedures⁵. Bis(phenylbiguanide)nickel(II) dichloride and bis(phenylbiguanide)copper(II) dichloride were prepared according to the reported method⁵.

Cu(ethylenedibiguanide)-doped Ni(ethylenedibiguanide): Nickel(II) sulphate hexahydrate (95% of 0.005 mol) and copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate (5% of 0.005 mol) were dissolved in water (40 ml). Ethylenedibiguanide sulphate (0.006 mol) was dissolved in a minimum amount of 4*N* NaOH and to it the above solution containing the metal ions was added slowly while stirring magnetically. pH of the mixture was adjusted to 10 with 4*N* NaOH. The separated precipitates were filtered under suction, washed thoroughly with water and then with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure at room temperature.

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In case of the other dibiguanides the Cu^{II}-doped complexes in the corresponding Ni^{II} complex matrix were prepared by following a similar procedure as described above.

[Ni(phenylbiguanide)₂]Cl₂·2H₂O was doped by recrystallising a mixture of the copper(II) and nickel(II) chloride complexes (5 : 95%, respectively) of the ligand from water.

Spectral and magnetic measurements : Electronic spectra (nujol) were recorded with the help of a Cary 14 spectrophotometer. Epr spectra were obtained on a Varian V45 02-12 X-band spectrometer with 100 kHz modulation. A cylindrical quartz sample tube was used for the spectra of powdered samples. A minute powdered sample of diphenylpicrylhydrazil free radical was used as a g-marker in a dual channel cavity and the frequency was monitored with the help of a frequency meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at room temperature by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the standard. Magnetic susceptibilities were corrected for diamagnetism of metal-ligand system⁶ and temperature-independent paramagnetism term using a value of 50 × 10⁻⁶ cgs unit.

Results and Discussion

The copper(II) complexes of the nitrogen donor ligands ethylenedibiguanide, trimethylenedibiguanide, *m*-phenylenedibiguanide, piperazinedibiguanide and phenylbiguanide were doped into the corresponding diamagnetic, square-planar nickel(II) complexes in order to obtain the magnetic dilution. Epr spectra of the polycrystalline samples of Cu(ethylenedibiguanide), Cu(trimethylenedibiguanide), Cu(*m*-phenylenedibiguanide), Cu(piperazinedibiguanide), and [Cu(phenylbiguanide)₂]Cl₂ exhibit a single exchange-narrowed line at *g*_{av} ~ 2.08 with a peak to peak separation of about 110 gauss. But the magnetic dilution in the corresponding square-planar and diamagnetic Ni^{II} complex matrix results in the resolution of the Cu^{II} nuclear hyperfine splittings and nitrogen superhyperfine splittings. The epr spectra of the complexes are comparable

to that of the Cu^{II} complex of biguanide⁴. The epr spectra appear to be axial and the spin-Hamiltonian constants obtained are given in Table 1. Epr data indicate that *g*_⊥ < *g*_∥, *A*_⊥^{Cu} < *A*_∥^{Cu} and *A*_⊥^N > *A*_∥^N and are according to the expectations. Kivelson and Neiman⁷ have indicated that *g*_∥ is a moderately sensitive parameter for predicting covalency. For covalent environments *g*_∥ is < 2.3 and for ionic environments *g*_∥ is usually ≥ 2.3. Thus, the epr data (Table 1) indicate that the metal-ligand bonding in the Cu^{II} complexes of ethylenedibiguanide, trimethylenedibiguanide, *m*-phenylenedibiguanide, piperazinedibiguanide, and phenylbiguanide are covalent⁷. The evaluation of the epr covalency parameters (discussed later) also supports this. The parameters *g*_⊥, *g*_∥, *A*_⊥^{Cu}, *A*_∥^{Cu}, *A*_⊥^N and *A*_∥^N were measured from the anisotropic spectra of the magnetically dilute polycrystalline solids. The observations of nine nitrogen superhyperfine lines on the high field 3/2 ↔ 3/2 copper hyperfine splitting components indicate the presence of four equivalent nitrogen atoms around Cu^{II} ion with CuN₄ chromophore which is consistent with the single crystal X-ray studies⁸. The epr spectra of the complexes are quite comparable with those of Cu(biguanide)₂ and Cu(*O*-methyl-amidinoarea)₂ which contain CuN₄ chromophore^{4,9}. There was no indication of more than two *g*-values in the epr spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes of the present ligands. This information and the occurrence of an electronic spectral band around 19 600 cm⁻¹ in these Cu^{II} complexes indicate also the presence of square-planar CuN₄ coordination sphere and *D*_{4h} symmetry for these complexes^{8,9}. The complexes exhibit room temperature magnetic moments in the range 1.76–1.80 B.M. and are magnetically dilute.

The σ bonding parameter¹⁰⁻¹², α_N³ was calculated from *A*_{av}^N. The α_N³ value (0.31–0.36) of the present complexes represents approximately the percent of electron delocalisation and thus the Cu^{II} unpaired electron (3*d*⁹) spends about 31–36% of its time in the nitrogen donor sites of the biguanide ligands. Thus, the epr evidence indicates that the unpaired *d*-electron of the metal ion is delocalised on to the ligands. A comparison of α_N³ values of the present

TABLE 1—SPIN-HAMILTONIAN CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Medium	<i>G</i>	<i>g</i> _{av} [*]	<i>g</i> _∥	<i>g</i> _⊥	<i>A</i> _∥ ^{Cu} / <i>A</i> _⊥ ^{Cu}		<i>A</i> _∥ ^N / <i>A</i> _⊥ ^N	
						× 10 ⁴ cm ⁻¹		× 10 ⁴ cm ⁻¹	
[Cu(ethylenedibiguanide)]	Powder	3.91	2.08	—	—	—	—	—	—
[Cu(ethylenedibiguanide)]	Ni ^{II} complex	3.91	2.10	2.19	2.05	209	32	11	14
[Cu(trimethylenedibiguanide)]	Ni ^{II} complex	3.50	2.09	2.17	2.05	220	33	12	15
[Cu(piperazinedibiguanide)]	Ni ^{II} complex	3.71	2.09	2.18	2.05	182	36	10	17
[Cu(<i>m</i> -phenylenedibiguanide)]	Ni ^{II} complex	3.29	2.09	2.16	2.05	169	35	12	16
[Cu(phenylbiguanide) ₂]Cl ₂	Ni ^{II} complex	3.29	2.09	2.16	2.05	188	35	15	17
[Cu(biguanide) ₂]	Ni ^{II} complex ^a	2.78	2.098	2.169	2.062	208	24	16 ^d	—
[Cu(phthalocyanine)]	Free ligand ^b	3.69	2.093	2.179	2.050	202	~19	16.7	—
[Cu(tetraphenylporphine)]	Chloroform, free ligand ^c	2.77	2.112	2.193	2.071	202	~29	15.9	—

* *g*_{av} = 1/3(*g*_∥ + 2*g*_⊥); *A*_{av} = 1/3(*A*_∥ + 2*A*_⊥). ^aRef. 4. ^bRef. 14. ^cRef. 13. ^d*A*_⊥^N.

Cu^{II} complexes with those of the Cu^{II} complexes with the acknowledged strong field ligands such as tetraphenylporphine ($\alpha_N^2 = 0.36$)¹³ and phthalocyanine ($\alpha_N^2 = 0.35$)¹⁴ indicates that biguanide and dibiguanides rank among the strong field ligands. The work of MacDonald¹⁵ has indicated that the position of ethylenedibiguanide in spectrochemical series is slightly below the strong field ligand cyanide ion. α_N^2 values of the complexes were found¹³ in the range 0.73–0.77.

The in-plane σ covalency parameter, α_{Cu}^2 was calculated using the expression given by Kivelson and Neiman¹²,

$$\alpha_{Cu}^2 = - \left(\frac{A_1}{0.036} \right) + (g_1 - 2.002) + \frac{2}{7}(g_1 - 2.002) + 0.04 \quad (1)$$

and was compared with the α_N^2 and α_N^1 . The α_{Cu}^2 value accounts for the fraction of the unpaired electron density situated on the Cu^{II} ion and is 0.71–0.84 for the present complexes. The α_N^1 values calculated from the nitrogen superhyperfine splittings are in general low in comparison to the analogous α_{Cu}^2 values, and thus $\alpha_N^1 \neq \alpha_{Cu}^2$. This discrepancy has been explained in terms of variation of copper 4s-electron density which has been assumed to be constant in equation (1)¹³. A comparison of these α_{Cu}^2 values with those of Cu^{II} tetraphenylporphine ($\alpha_{Cu}^2 = 0.82$)¹³ and Cu^{II} phthalocyanine ($\alpha_{Cu}^2 = 0.80$)¹⁴ indicates the similarity of the present biguanide complexes with the Cu^{II} complexes of strong field ligands phthalocyanine and tetraphenylporphine, all having CuN₄ chromophere.

In D_{4h} symmetry Cu^{II} complexes with a $^2B_{1g}$ ground state g -values are given¹⁶ by

$$g_1 = 2.002 - 8k_1^2 \lambda_0 / \Delta E_{zy}$$

$$\text{and } g_1 = 2.002 - 2k_1^2 \lambda_0 / \Delta E_{xx}$$

where, k 's are the orbital reduction factors. The combination of the above two expressions leads to

$$G = \frac{(g_1 - 2.002)}{(g_1 - 2.002)} = \frac{4k_1^2 \Delta E_{xx}}{k_1^2 \Delta E_{zy}}$$

If the G value is < 4.0 , the ligands forming the Cu^{II} complexes are regarded as strong field ligands¹⁷. The G values for the present complexes are in the range 3.29–3.91 and indicate the strong field nature of the ligands biguanides and dibiguanides. G values of the present complexes are comparable to those of Cu^{II} complexes of strong field ligands tetraphenylporphine ($G = 2.77$)¹³ and phthalocyanine ($G = 3.69$)¹⁴.

A comparison of the spin-Hamiltonian parameters and bonding parameters (α_N^2 , α_N^1 , α_{Cu}^2) of the

present Cu^{II} dibiguanide complexes containing the bridging group with those of the Cu^{II} complexes of biguanide and phenylbiguanide in which no bridging group is present, indicates that the nature of the bridging groups in dibiguanides has little effect on the epr spectra and bonding parameters. Similar observations were also noticed in epr spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes of biguanide and dibiguanides¹⁸. The bridging groups like $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$ etc. bridge two biguanide molecules in one side (2–5) leaving the other side unbridged. The bridging in both the sides would produce a macrocyclic ligand in which case a pronounced effect of the bridging groups is expected to be noticed. Thus, the one sided bridging and the absence of a macrocyclic system do not effect appreciably the delocalisation of electrons in comparison to the non-bridging system (1 and 6) as is evident from the bonding parameters.

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